

Enhancing coordination abilities in freestyle wrestlers through special exercises and improving competition effectiveness

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Abstract

This article provides scientific-theoretical and practical justification for the targeted and systematic development of coordination abilities in the training process of freestyle wrestlers. The study analyzes the direct influence of coordination abilities (movement accuracy, balance maintenance, quick adaptability, spatial orientation, movement harmony, and differentiation ability) on technical and tactical effectiveness in freestyle wrestling.

The work reveals mechanisms for improving wrestlers' ability to make quick decisions in complex dynamic situations, adapt to counteractions, and execute technical elements with high precision through a specially selected set of exercises. It is also recommended to apply coordination loads progressively, taking into account age, skill level, and functional preparedness indicators.

The research results show that integrating specially directed coordination exercises into the training process significantly increases the effectiveness, stability, and speed of athletes' adequate responses to opponents' actions in competitive conditions. As a result, the overall effectiveness of competitive activity and victory indicators improve.

Keywords: Freestyle wrestling, special exercise, coordination, competition, athlete, wrestler, system, exercises.

Introduction

Currently, the work and innovations being implemented in the education and sports systems of many countries worldwide necessitate the consistent development of these areas. In particular, the intensification of global competition in wrestling is clearly manifested by the growing number of countries participating in freestyle wrestling at the Olympic Games.

Object of research: The training processes and competitive activities of freestyle wrestlers at the Uzbekistan State University of Physical Education and Sport.

Subject of research: The system of special exercises aimed at developing the coordination abilities of freestyle wrestlers and its influence on competitive activity.

Purpose of the research: To analyze the training and competitive processes of qualified freestyle wrestlers to develop their coordination abilities and increase competitive effectiveness.

Research objectives:

Development of a system of special exercises performed individually and in pairs, contributing to the development of coordination abilities.

Methods

The study used such methods as analysis of scientific and methodological literature, pedagogical observation, pedagogical testing, pulsometry, pedagogical experiment, and mathematical statistics.

Result and discussion

Performing the arm-around-neck throw technique for 10 repetitions took 21.99 ± 2.01 seconds in the experimental group and 21.49 ± 2.07 seconds in the control group. Executing the chest throw technique for 10 repetitions took 22.99 ± 2.03 seconds in the experimental group and 22.20 ± 2.08 seconds in the control group. Performing the shoulder throw technique for 10 repetitions took 20.99 ± 2.01 seconds in the experimental group and 20.79 ± 2.07 seconds in the control group. The time taken to execute the over-the-shoulders throw technique for 10 repetitions was 21.90 ± 2.03 seconds in the experimental group and 21.70 ± 2.06 seconds in the control group. Performing entry movements for techniques 10 times took 18.90 ± 1.83 seconds in the experimental group and 19.70 ± 2.06 seconds in the control group. At the beginning of the study, no significant differences were observed in the reliability of all indicators obtained from performing these 10 exercises.

We analyzed the physical fitness state of athletes in the research group, based on the training program we implemented in practice. The physical fitness indicators of wrestlers at the end of the study are presented in Table. As shown in the table, performing three circular runs on the Kurash mat in a bridge position to the right and left took 13.49 ± 1.24 seconds in the experimental group, while this indicator was 15.43 ± 1.47 seconds in the control group.

Table 1. Indicators of the performance of special exercises by athletes in the experimental and control groups at the beginning of the study (n=24)

No.	Control tests	Experimental group			Control group		
		\bar{X}	σ	V%	\bar{X}	σ	V%
1.	Circular runs on the wrestling mat in bridge position, 3 times to the right and left (s).	15.99	1.54	9.6	16.13	1.57	9.7
2.	Climbing a 4-meter rope (times)	1.98	0.21	10.6	2.05	0.19	9.3
3.	Standing long jump (cm).	1.97	0.70	12.14	1.99	0.74	12.12
4.	3x10m shuttle run (s)	7.78	0.75	9.4	7.47	0.76	9.4
5.	Executing 10 waist throw techniques (s)	20.95	2.03	9.7	20.58	2.09	11
6.	Executing 10 arm wrap around neck throw techniques (s)	21.99	2.01	10.6	21.49	2.07	11.6
7.	Executing 10 chest throw techniques (s)	22.99	2.03	11.0	22.20	2.08	11.9
8.	Executing 10 shoulder throw techniques (s)	20.99	2.01	10.5	20.79	2.07	10.9
9.	Executing 10 over-the-shoulders throw techniques (s)	21.90	2.03	11.1	21.70	2.06	11.5
10.	Executing 10 technique entry movements (s)	18.90	1.83	10.9	19.70	2.06	11.5

Climbing a 4-meter rope was achieved 2.75 ± 0.19 times in the experimental group and 2.03 ± 0.21 times in the control group. The standing long jump distance was 2.20 ± 0.60 cm in the experimental group and 2 ± 0.51 cm in the control group. The time spent on the 3x10m shuttle run was 7.25 ± 0.72 seconds in the experimental group and 7.50 ± 0.75 seconds in the control group. Performing 10 waist throws took 19.33 ± 2.0 seconds in the experimental group and 20.0 ± 2.04 seconds in the control group. Executing the arm-around-neck throw tech-

nique 10 times took 20.03 ± 1.81 seconds in the experimental group and 21.39 ± 2.0 seconds in the control group. Performing the chest throw technique 10 times took 20.99 ± 2.01 seconds in the experimental group and 21.12 ± 2.08 seconds in the control group.

The execution of the shoulder throw technique in 10 attempts (s) in the experimental group took 18.30 ± 1.71 seconds, and in the control group - 20.48 ± 2.02 seconds. The time taken for performing the over-the-shoulder throw technique in 10 attempts in the experimental

Table 2. Indicators of special exercise performance by athletes in the experimental and control groups at the end of the study (n=24)

No.	Control tests	Research group			Control group		
		\bar{X}	σ	V%	\bar{X}	σ	V%
1.	Circular runs on the wrestling mat in bridge position, 3 times to the right and left (s)	13.49	1.24	9.6	15.43	1.47	9.7
2.	Climbing a 4-meter rope (times)	2.75	0.19	9.3	2.03	0.21	10.6
3.	Standing long jump (cm)	2.20	0.60	12.14	2	0.51	12.12
4.	3x10m shuttle run (s)	7.25	0.72	9.4	7.50	0.75	9.4
5.	Performing waist throw technique 10 times (s)	19.33	2.0	9.7	20.0	2.04	11.0
6.	Performing arm-wrap throw technique 10 times (s)	20.03	1.81	10.6	21.39	2.0	11.4
7.	Performing chest throw technique 10 times (s)	20.99	2.01	10.9	21.12	2.08	11.6
8.	Performing shoulder throw technique 10 times (s)	18.30	1.71	10.3	20.48	2.02	10.9
9.	Performing over-the-shoulders throw technique 10 times (s)	20.42	1.95	11.0	21.57	2.01	11.2
10.	Performing entry movements for techniques 10 times (s)	15.68	1.53	10.6	18.54	2.04	11.4

Table 3. Comparative analysis of the performance of special exercises by athletes in the experimental and control groups

No.	Control tests	At the beginning of the study				At the end of the study				At the end of the study	
		EG		CG		EG		CG		At the beginning	At the end
		$\bar{X} \pm \sigma$	$\bar{X} \pm \sigma$	$\bar{X} \pm \sigma$	$\bar{X} \pm \sigma$	$\bar{X} \pm \sigma$	$\bar{X} \pm \sigma$				
1.	Circular runs on the wrestling mat in bridge position 3 times to the right and left (s).	15.99	1.54	16.13	1.57	13.49	1.24	15.43	1.47	p>0.05	p<0.05
2.	Climbing a 4-meter rope (times)	2.05	0.19	1.98	0.21	2.75	0.19	2.03	0.21	p>0.05	p>0.05
3.	Standing long jump (m)	1.97	0.70	1.99	0.74	2.20	0.60	2	0.51	p>0.05	p<0.05
4.	3x10m shuttle run (s)	7.78	0.75	7.47	0.76	7.25	0.72	7.50	0.75	p>0.05	p>0.05
5.	Execution of over-the-waist throw technique 10 times (s)	20.95	2.03	20.58	2.09	19.33	2.0	20.0	2.04	p>0.05	p<0.05
6.	Execution of arm-around-the-neck throw technique 10 times (s)	21.99	2.01	21.49	2.07	20.03	1.81	21.39	2.0	p>0.05	p<0.05
7.	Execution of over-the-chest throw technique 10 times (s)	22.99	2.03	22.20	2.08	20.99	2.01	21.12	2.08	p>0.05	p<0.05
8.	Execution of over-the-shoulder throw technique 10 times (s)	20.99	2.01	20.79	2.07	18.30	1.71	20.48	2.02	p>0.05	p<0.05
9.	Execution of over-both-shoulders throw technique 10 times (s)	21.90	2.03	21.70	2.06	20.42	1.95	21.57	2.01	p>0.05	p<0.05
10.	Execution of entry movements for techniques 10 times (s)	18.90	1.83	19.70	2.06	15.68	1.53	18.54	2.04	p>0.05	p<0.05

group was 20.42 ± 1.95 seconds, in the control group - 21.57 ± 2.01 seconds.

Performance of entry movements in 10 attempts (s) in the experimental group was 15.68 ± 1.53 seconds, in the control group - 18.54 ± 2.04 seconds. Based on the training program implemented in practice, we analyzed the physical fitness state of athletes. A comparative analysis of the dynamics of physical fitness indicators of wrestlers in the experimental and control groups showed that optimizing the ratio of physical fitness and rationally regulating loads makes it possible to achieve significant changes important for the preparation of highly qualified athletes.

In the 10-second over-the-shoulder throw exercise, the initial results were 20.99 ± 2.01 in the experimental group (EG) and 20.79 ± 2.07 in the control group (CG). At the end of the study, these indicators were 18.30 ± 1.71 and 20.48 ± 2.02 , respectively, with the difference being statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). In the 10-second exercise for performing over-the-shoulder throws, the initial results were 21.90 ± 2.03 in the EG and 21.70 ± 2.06 in the CG. At the end of the study, these indicators were 20.42 ± 1.95 and 21.57 ± 2.01 , respectively, with the difference being statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). In the 10-second exercise for

performing entry movements, the initial results were 18.90 ± 1.83 in the EG and 19.70 ± 2.06 in the CG. At the end of the study, these indicators were 15.68 ± 1.53 and 18.54 ± 2.04 , respectively, with the difference being statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). According to the comparative analysis of the indicators in this table, 8 out of 10 indicators showed a high level of reliability. At the end of the study, a statistically significant 80% increase in the arithmetic mean of the EG indicators was observed compared to the changes in the same indicators in the control group during the experiment (8 out of 10 indicators were reliable). This demonstrates the effectiveness of the developed technology and the achievement of the intended goal of the pedagogical experiment.

Conclusion

To address the shortcomings in the training of qualified freestyle wrestlers, a survey was conducted among experienced specialists and athletes, and their responses were collected. Additionally, practical work was carried out through pedagogical observation and monitoring of wrestlers' self-control during the training process. Throughout the year, an optimized ratio of general physical training, special physical training, and technical-tactical training was im-

plemented in the weekly cycle for the experimental group's training process. Based on the analysis, it can be concluded that coordination abilities, technical-tactical actions, and physical qualities play a crucial role in improving the sportsmanship of freestyle wrestlers.

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Freestyle wrestling, theory and methodology of wrestling training, athlete performance analysis, theory of physical education and sport, competition analysis in wrestling.

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